

MIGRAINE AND CREATIVITY: AN EXAMINATION OF CREATIVE THINKING ABILITIES FROM A NEUROLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

Keywords

Creativity,

Cognitive Function,

Psychosocial Factors,

Disability Evaluation

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ABSTRACT

To examine creative thinking tendencies in interictal migraine and their associations with aura status, anxiety, and migraine burden. In this cross-sectional observational study, forty-three adults with migraine diagnosed according to International Headache Society (2018) criteria were assessed during the interictal period. Creativity was measured with the Marmara Creative Thinking Tendencies Scale (MCTTS); anxiety and depressive symptoms with the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). Weekly attack frequency, attack duration, and Migraine Disability Assessment (MIDAS) indexed clinical burden. Creativity scores did not differ by aura status ($p = 0.531$). Higher creativity was associated with lower attack frequency, shorter attack duration, lower MIDAS scores, and lower anxiety and depression (all $p < 0.05$). In multiple linear regression, higher BAI remained independently and inversely associated with creativity ($B = -0.341$, $p = 0.020$), while attack frequency was retained at a trend level ($B = -3.614$, $p = 0.082$; $R^2 = 0.258$). Creative thinking tendencies vary substantially among individuals with migraine and show inverse associations with psychosocial symptoms and migraine burden, independent of aura status.

INTRODUCTION

Recurrent and debilitating migraine attacks create a significant burden beyond pain, often disrupting daily life activities due to accompanying sensory hypersensitivities and autonomic symptoms.^{1,2} Parallel to this clinical burden, interest in the variability in cognitive performance that may occur throughout the migraine cycle has grown.^{3,4} Quantitative studies conducted during attacks have reported alterations in multiple cognitive domains, including attention, memory, visuospatial skills, and executive functions; these assessments have generally been conducted under different conditions based on task requirements and clinical context.^{3,5} Studies addressing the interictal period, however, present more variable results; while some studies indicate measurable differences in specific cognitive measures, others report performance largely similar to that of non-migraine samples, highlighting the heterogeneity of findings and the need for cautious interpretation.^{3,4,6,7}

Creativity can be defined as a mental capacity that can reveal previously unnoticed relationships and possibilities; in this sense, it goes beyond merely producing a product and brings a new perspective to the world. Creative production often requires taking an idea that others have overlooked seriously and persisting in the process of developing it.^{8,9} This capacity is characterized not by unidimensional traits, but by a "complex" structure in which seemingly contradictory tendencies and characteristics can coexist in the same person.^{5,10} The creative process is not a single mental act; it is a multidimensional sequence in which perception, memory, imagination, reasoning, motivation, and emotion work together. Creative ideas emerge through the overcoming of conventional patterns of knowledge, the combination of abstract mental images, and the transfer of information to different contexts. These areas are not independent of each other, but each represents specific creative forms in which different cognitive, emotional, and experiential processes prevail.

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In migraine research, creativity has mostly been addressed descriptively through artistic representations of visual experiences accompanying migraine auras; these productions are generally created based on memory after the experience itself, and the existing body of knowledge relies heavily on historical examples, clinical observations, exhibition studies, and case narratives¹¹⁻¹³ Therefore, creativity is a dynamic interaction of both cognitive and emotional processes. This descriptive emphasis may have relatively limited the quantitative examination of broader and measurable dimensions of creativity. Although the Marmara Creative Thinking Tendencies Scale, consisting of 25 items and 6 dimensions, does not cover all of an individual's creative thinking tendencies, it has been developed for adults, has undergone validity and reliability studies in Turkish, and assesses basic tendencies such as self-discipline, novelty seeking, courage, curiosity, skepticism, and flexibility, which are consistent with the theoretical framework of the study. For these reasons, the Marmara Creative Thinking Tendencies Scale (MCTTS) was chosen as an appropriate and practical measurement tool for this study because, although it does not directly measure attention, memory, or executive functions, its subscales are indirectly related to processes such as cognitive flexibility, executive control, associative thinking, and problem solving.¹⁴

Existing evidence on creativity in the context of migraine is limited, particularly regarding whether measurable dimensions of creativity differ across migraine subtypes during the interictal period. Although migraine has been studied in relation to various cognitive and emotional domains, there are relatively few studies that focus on creativity using quantitative and operational measures and directly compare migraine subgroups with healthy controls. Therefore, this study aims to partially fill this gap in the literature by examining how performance or trait indicators related to creativity during the interictal period are patterned across different migraine subtypes and non-migraine populations, based on standardized and comparative approaches.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Center Where Conducted

This single-center, observational study was conducted at the Neurology Outpatient Clinic of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Faculty of Medicine. Data collection began on July 9, 2025, and continued for six months. Patients diagnosed with migraine according to the 2018 International Headache Society

(IHS) diagnostic criteria were included in the study. The main objective of the study was to evaluate creative thinking tendencies in individuals diagnosed with migraine during the interictal period. The methodological approach was based on previous studies examining the relationship between migraine and creativity.

Participants and Sample Size

A total of 43 patients who applied to the Neurology Outpatient Clinic of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University and met the IHS 2018 migraine diagnostic criteria were included in the study. The sample size was limited due to socioeconomic difficulties, financial constraints, and difficulties in accessing healthcare services in the post-earthquake period. These factors led to a significant decrease in clinic visits. Therefore, the sample size reflects the clinically accessible patient population during the period when the study was conducted. Patients who declined to participate in the study or who were unable to complete the assessment scales were not included in the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria were determined as follows:

- (i) Being between the ages of 18 and 65,
- (ii) Having visited the Neurology Outpatient Clinic at Hatay Mustafa Kemal University as an outpatient,
- (iii) Having been diagnosed with migraine according to the IHS 2018 diagnostic criteria,
- (iv) Being in the interictal period during the evaluation (not exhibiting migraine attack, prodromal, or postdromal symptoms),
- (v) Being able to read and write Turkish,
- (vi) Have provided written informed consent.

Exclusion criteria are defined as follows:

- (i) Presence of major neurological diseases such as epilepsy, Parkinson's disease, or multiple sclerosis;
- (ii) Presence of severe psychiatric disorders such as schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, or major depression;
- (iii) Having a diagnosis of another primary headache disorder;
- (iv) The presence of severe cognitive impairment or communication difficulties that could affect the assessment;
- (v) Use of medications that could affect neuropsychological function (e.g., high-dose sedatives or antipsychotics) within the past three months;
- (vi) Inability to independently read and complete assessment scales.

Assessment Timing and Confirmation of the Interictal Period

All assessments were conducted during the interictal period to minimize the impact of recent migraine attacks. Prior to

assessment, participants were asked whether they had reported any symptoms of a migraine attack, prodromal, or postdromal period. Assessments of individuals thought to be in any of these periods were postponed and rescheduled when the necessary conditions were met.

Data Collection Tools and Application

Data were collected using the Sociodemographic and Clinical Information Form developed by the researchers, the Marmara Creative Thinking Tendencies Scale (MCTTS), the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI), the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), and the Migraine Disability Assessment (MIDAS) scale. The Sociodemographic and Clinical Information Form recorded demographic characteristics such as age, gender, and education level, as well as migraine-specific clinical variables such as disease duration, weekly attack frequency, attack duration, presence of aura, and current treatments. Creative thinking tendencies were quantitatively assessed using the Marmara Creative Thinking Tendencies Scale (MCTTS), a 25-item self-report instrument rated on a 5-point Likert scale.

The severity of anxiety symptoms was assessed using the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI). The BAI is a 21-item self-report scale developed for adults. Each item is rated on a scale of 0–3 (0 = none, 3 = severe), and the total score ranges from 0 to 63. The scale inquires about the level of anxiety symptoms "in the past week, including today"; higher total scores indicate higher anxiety severity. The validity and reliability of the Turkish version of the scale have been demonstrated in a Turkish sample.

The level of depressive symptoms was assessed using the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). The BDI is a 21-item self-report scale, with each item scored from 0 to 3; the total score is calculated on a scale of 0–63. The scale aims to assess the severity of depressive symptoms "in the past week, including today"; higher scores are consistent with higher depressive symptom severity. Validity and reliability studies of the Turkish version of the scale have been reported in Turkish samples.

Migraine-related functional impairment and disability were assessed using the Migraine Disability Assessment (MIDAS) scale. MIDAS is a 5-item self-report scale that asks about the number of days lost in the last 3 months due to headaches, resulting in absence from work/school, reduced work/school performance, limitations in household activities, and inability to participate in social activities. The total MIDAS score is obtained by summing the number of days for the first 5 items;

higher scores indicate higher migraine-related disability/functional impairment. The validity and reliability of the Turkish version of the scale have been demonstrated in a multicenter study (Ertaş et al., Turkish MIDAS validity–reliability).

All assessments were conducted during the interictal period by questioning participants about their current pain status and attack-specific symptoms, with the aim of minimizing the impact of migraine attack acute effects on measurements. Prior to the assessment, participants were asked whether they were currently experiencing migraine headache and whether they had any prodromal or postdromal symptoms; measurements for individuals assessed to be in either of these periods were postponed and rescheduled when appropriate conditions were available. All assessments were conducted face-to-face in a quiet environment free from distracting stimuli; participants completed the scales independently, and only necessary explanations regarding the scale instructions were provided.

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University (Decision No: 02; Date: July 9, 2025). The research was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Helsinki Declaration, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 23.0. In descriptive statistics, categorical variables were presented as numbers and percentages [n, %]; continuous variables were reported as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) to reflect the uncertainty in the estimation of the sample mean. Creativity scores were categorized into low–medium and high groups using the sample median as the cutoff point.

Tests used for comparisons between two independent groups were selected based on an assessment of the distribution characteristics of continuous variables and the appropriateness of parametric test assumptions (particularly normality of distribution and homogeneity of variance). When the assumptions were met, the Student t-test for independent samples was used as the parametric method; when the assumptions were not met or the distribution showed significant deviation, the Mann–Whitney U test was used as the non-parametric method. In this context, the Mann–Whitney U test was applied to compare clinical and

psychometric variables according to creativity levels (low–medium vs. high). The Mann–Whitney U test was used to compare clinical and psychometric variables according to migraine subtypes (with aura vs. without aura), while the Student's t-test was used to compare creativity scores according to subtypes.

Relationships between continuous variables were examined using Spearman's correlation coefficient to provide an approach that is independent of distribution assumptions and sensitive to ordinal relationships. Multiple linear regression analysis was performed to evaluate the relationship between creativity scores (dependent variable) and age, clinical variables related to migraine, and psychometric measurements (independent variables). Due to the limited sample size, the regression analysis was planned within an exploratory/hypothesis-generating framework rather than for causal inference; variables that did not contribute statistically significantly were gradually removed from the model using the backward elimination method to reduce the model to a more parsimonious structure.

Two-tailed p-values were reported for all tests. $p < 0.05$ was accepted as the threshold for statistical significance; considering the limited sample size and the exploratory nature of the findings, results in the range of $p = 0.05–0.10$ were additionally noted as "statistical trends" and were not interpreted as significant. There were no missing data for the variables included in the analyses.

RESULTS

When examining the gender distribution of participants, it was found that the majority of the sample consisted of women (83.7%; $n = 36$), while men constituted 16.3% of the sample ($n = 7$). When evaluated according to their creativity levels, 62.8% of participants ($n = 27$) were classified as having low-to-moderate creativity levels, while 37.2% ($n = 16$) were determined to have high creativity levels. When examining the distribution of migraine subtypes, 51.2% of cases ($n = 22$) were diagnosed with migraine without aura, and 48.8% ($n = 21$) with migraine with aura (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants

Sex	Female	36	83.7
	Male	7	16.3
Creativity level	Low–Moderate	27	62.8
	High	16	37.2
Migraine type	Without aura	22	51.2
	With aura		

The mean age of the participants was calculated as 39.95 ± 1.76 years (median: 44.00). The mean creativity score was 88.51 ± 2.79 , with scores ranging from 39 to 117. Looking at the psychological assessment scales, the mean scores for the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) were 21.40 ± 2.89 and 21.53 ± 2.51 , respectively. In terms of clinical characteristics related to migraine, participants reported a weekly average attack frequency of 2.93 ± 0.20 , an average attack duration of 7.56 ± 1.68 hours, and an average MIDAS score of 13.42 ± 1.28 (Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of participants' age and psychometric characteristics

Age (years)	39.95	1.76	11.57	44.00	18.00	63.00
Creativity score	88.51	2.79	18.32	91.00	39.00	117.00
BAI score	21.40	2.89	18.98	14.00	3.00	60.00
BDI score	21.53	2.51	16.47	15.00	4.00	58.00
Weekly attack frequency	2.93	0.20	1.32	3.00	1.00	5.00
Attack duration (hours)	7.56	1.68	11.04	4.00	1.00	72.00
MIDAS score	13.42	1.28	8.42	10.00	2.00	26.00

Participants' clinical and psychometric data were compared according to their creativity levels (low–medium and high), and the results are presented (Table 3). Although the mean scores on the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) were numerically higher in the high creativity group, these differences did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.107$ and $p = 0.237$, respectively). Similarly, no statistically significant differences were found between the creativity groups in terms of weekly migraine attack frequency ($p = 0.837$), attack duration ($p = 0.416$), and MIDAS scores ($p = 0.984$). (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of clinical and psychometric characteristics according to creativity levels

BAI score	17.67 ± 3.15 (12.00 [3–52])	27.69 ± 5.45 (18.50 [4–60])	0.107†
BDI score	19.00 ± 2.96 (15.00 [4–55])	25.81 ± 4.45 (21.50 [4–58])	0.237†
Weekly attack frequency	2.96 ± 0.27 (3.00 [1–5])	2.88 ± 0.30 (2.50 [1–5])	0.837†
Attack duration (hours)	9.04 ± 2.62 (4.00 [1–72])	5.06 ± 0.74 (4.00 [2–10])	0.416†
MIDAS score	13.19 ± 1.62 (10.00 [2–26])	13.81 ± 2.18 (14.00 [2–24])	0.984†

Clinical and psychometric data for the participants were evaluated by migraine type (with aura vs. without aura) and are presented. The two groups showed statistically similar distributions for creativity scores, Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) scores, Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) scores, and MIDAS scores (all $p > 0.05$). However, when weekly attack frequency was examined, the mean was higher in the migraine with aura group (3.29 ± 0.24) than in the migraine without aura group (2.59 ± 0.31), with this difference approaching statistical significance ($p = 0.065$). No significant difference was observed between the groups in terms of attack duration ($p = 0.484$) (Table 4).

Table 4. Comparison of clinical and psychometric characteristics according to migraine type

Creativity score	86.77 ± 3.98 (90.50 [39–117])	90.33 ± 3.97 (91.00 [55–116])	0.531‡
BAI score	17.73 ± 3.77 (12.00 [3–60])	25.24 ± 4.36 (16.00 [3–60])	0.162†
BDI score	19.36 ± 3.08 (17.00 [4–55])	23.81 ± 4.02 (15.00 [4–58])	0.488†
Weekly attack frequency	2.59 ± 0.31 (2.00 [1–5])	3.29 ± 0.24 (3.00 [2–5])	0.065†
Attack duration (hours)	8.32 ± 3.14 (4.00 [1–72])	6.76 ± 1.15 (4.00 [2–24])	0.484†
MIDAS score	12.27 ± 1.66 (9.00 [2–24])	14.62 ± 1.98 (15.00 [2–26])	0.330†

Correlation analysis was performed to examine the relationships between variables. Accordingly, higher creativity levels were associated with lower weekly attack frequency ($r = -0.417$; $p < 0.01$), shorter attack duration ($r = -0.334$; $p < 0.05$), and lower MIDAS scores ($r = -0.404$; $p < 0.01$). Similarly, creativity scores showed a negative correlation with anxiety (BAI: $r = -0.368$; $p < 0.05$) and depression (BDI: $r = -0.329$; $p < 0.05$) levels. In contrast, positive correlations were found between indicators reflecting migraine burden (attack frequency, attack duration, and MIDAS scores) and psychological measures (BAI and BDI), and these relationships are shown (Table 5).

Table 5. Correlation matrix showing relationships among variables

Creativity	–			
BAI	–0.368*	–		
BDI	–0.329*	0.622***	–	
Weekly attack frequency	–0.417**	0.419**	0.441**	–
Attack duration	–0.334*	0.307*	0.565***	0.367* –
MIDAS	–0.404**	0.517***	0.518***	0.513* 0.536* –
			**	**

Variables that were not statistically significant in the multiple linear regression model and were therefore excluded from the model are presented in order (Table 6, Table 7). According to the final model, anxiety level (BAI) was found to be statistically significantly related to creativity scores ($p = 0.020$); weekly attack frequency remained in the model at the trend level ($p = 0.082$). The variables together explained approximately 26% of the variance in creativity scores, and the model was found to be statistically significant overall ($R^2 = 0.258$; $p < 0.001$). The regression equation obtained from the analysis is as follows: Creativity score = $106.405 - (0.341 \times \text{BAI}) - (3.614 \times \text{Weekly attack frequency})$. According to this model, a one-unit increase in BAI and weekly attack frequency is associated with a decrease of 0.341 and 3.614 units in creativity score, respectively.

Table 6. Results of the multiple linear regression analysis

Constant	106.405	6.142	17.324	<0.001
BAI score	–0.341	0.141	–2.427	0.020
Weekly attack frequency	–3.614	2.028	–1.782	0.082

Table 7. Variables excluded from the regression model

Age	–0.028	–0.194	0.847
BDI score	–0.094	–0.527	0.601
Attack duration	–0.086	–0.630	0.533
MIDAS score	–0.128	–0.754	0.456

DISCUSSION

This study examined creative thinking tendencies in individuals with migraine within a multidimensional framework, considering their clinical characteristics, migraine subtypes, and psychosocial variables. Although previous studies have suggested that individuals with migraine may produce fewer creative ideas compared to healthy controls during the interictal period¹⁵, the analyses in this study were conducted only within the migraine sample. Therefore, the findings answer the question of what characteristics vary among individuals with migraine along with creative thinking tendencies, rather than differences between patients and controls. Creative thinking tendency scores within the sample showed marked heterogeneity; higher levels of creative thinking tendency were concentrated in a relatively small subgroup. This suggests that creative thinking tendencies in individuals with migraine are not a uniform trait and that there

are significant differences between individuals. Comparisons based on migraine subtypes revealed no significant difference in creative thinking tendency scores between the aura and non-aura migraine groups, suggesting that subtype classification alone may not be a distinguishing feature of creative thinking tendencies; suggesting that variability in creative thinking tendencies may be better understood in the context of individual differences and accompanying psychosocial burden rather than clinical subtype.^{16, 17}

Findings related to psychological variables indicate that there may be an inverse relationship between anxiety level and creative thinking tendency scores; higher BAI scores were observed to be associated with lower levels of creative thinking tendencies. Although average anxiety levels are similar across subtypes, it is possible that individual anxiety variability within the sample is related to variability in creative thinking tendencies; this suggests that the assessment is based on how inter-individual differences change together rather than on group averages. This finding is consistent with previous studies reporting that anxiety may be negatively related to creativity, particularly in tasks requiring different thinking and artistic production.¹⁸

Furthermore, the observation that higher creative thinking tendency scores are associated with lower attack frequency and less migraine burden/severity presents a noteworthy pattern; however, the direction of this relationship or whether it reflects a migraine-specific effect cannot be determined from these data. A more cautious interpretation suggests that the variability associated with creative thinking tendencies may be changing in tandem with migraine burden through processes related to stress and anxiety.

Studies in non-migraine populations reporting reductions in stress measures across various creative activity contexts are also consistent with this framework.¹⁶ Finally, the absence of a control group or normative comparison and the cross-sectional design limit inferences about the direction and specificity of these relationships.

Limitations

The cross-sectional design of this study does not allow for causal inferences. The relatively small sample size may be related to transportation difficulties, limited access to healthcare services, and the tendency of individuals to seek care primarily at nearby healthcare facilities following the earthquake that affected Hatay province on February 6, 2023. Therefore, the sample reflects a group with a specific

geographic and healthcare access profile, limiting the generalizability of the findings to the broader migraine population. Furthermore, potential confounding variables such as fatigue, decreased attention, cognitive functions, and sleep patterns, which could affect both migraine burden and measures related to creativity or anxiety, were not systematically assessed. Therefore, caution should be exercised in interpreting the observed relationships. In the future, longitudinal designs considering different phases of migraine (preictal, ictal, and postictal) conducted with larger, multicenter samples, and when appropriate, creativity-based studies are expected to more clearly reveal the direction, temporal dynamics, and clinical significance of the relationships between creativity, anxiety, and migraine burden.

CONCLUSION

It has been observed that creative thinking tendencies in individuals diagnosed with migraine during the interictal period can vary between individuals. Higher levels of creativity have been found to be associated with lower migraine burden and lower anxiety levels, independent of aura status. Anxiety is thought to be one of the psychosocial factors that may be inversely related to creative thinking tendencies in the context of migraine. It is believed that the assessment of creativity-related characteristics may offer potential contributions to more individualized and psychosocially sensitive approaches to migraine management.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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